

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

IMPLEMENTATION OF INDICATORS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE ENTERPRISE'S OPERATING ACTIVITIES IN THE SYSTEM OF FORMALIZED MANAGEMENT OF CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the solution of an important scientific problem – the formation of a strategic performance management system and the adaptation of enterprises implementing construction projects to changes. Theoretical approaches to the classification of strategic performance of enterprises are studied and systematized, which made it possible to highlight the need to take into account predictable and unpredictable possibilities of changes in the enterprise, focusing on external and internal factors of the enterprise environment, which, respectively, influence the formation of the quality management system. The theoretical and methodological approach to the formation of the management system is based on the formation and implementation of the main elements and constituent components (organizational, economic, legal, technological and social) with the use of methods and techniques of a mixed approach (managerial, functional and process).

Keywords: construction enterprise, investment project, economic performance, operational system of enterprise management, change management.

Operational activity is purposeful activity to create any of what utility (any material and immaterial goods). Covers and the production of material products, and the provision of services, and the performance of any other jobs in any field of activity. The operating system is one of the components (systems) of the organization that implements the operational function, i.e. production of products and provision of services external to the organization to consumers.

Consequences of a long crisis that until recently covered the whole the construction industry of Ukraine, forces construction enterprises as the leading ones stakeholders (executors of works, which are in the format of investment projects, which ensure the creation of finished and unfinished construction products), to search for effective means of getting out of a state of shaky balance or destruction. The dynamism and high degree of uncertainty of the external environment negatively affect the efficiency of domestic construction companies enterprises, force modern organizations to transform into more and more complex systems. It becomes the basis of their adaptive diffusion into the competitive environment competition not only of goods or services, but also of innovative technologies management. The leading and systemic means of exiting the crisis and destructive situations for construction enterprises, as well as others industrial enterprises, there is an innovative activity strategy, radical or partial transformation (modernization) of the company's operating system and the system and structure of the administration of its activities operating at the enterprise. The innovative focus of process-oriented technology is enterprise management organization as a network of interconnected processes, where obtaining an effective result is achieved when the activities are appropriate resources are managed as a process.

Implementation of the process approach allows you to systematically connect with each other functional areas of activity, to build transparent and understandable for employees of the enterprise schemes for the implementation of management tasks, evaluate and optimize resources. The ability of management to form and use a system of indicators and criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of managerial implementation decisions in each implemented process, at each stage of production or of the management chain makes it possible to promptly detect undesirable deviations from the given standards of activity and eliminate them by eliminating weak links business processes that reduce the overall efficiency of economic activity. Specificity of the process-oriented technology of ensuring the quality of management is determined by the fact that it actually allows erasing the boundaries between management product quality and management of the enterprise itself.

Therefore, a number of methodological and scientific-applied problems of the functioning of construction enterprises appear on the agenda:

- separate improvement tools (reengineering, restructuring, rehabilitation) in autonomous use do not provide adequate performance as means of overcoming processes of stagnation or crisis phenomena in the activity of the mentioned enterprises;

- taking into account the multi-project nature of the functioning of the operating room systems of the construction enterprise and the content of its business processes arise difficulties in coordinating content, time and resources for tasks strategic renewal with the operational cycle of construction enterprises and investment and construction cycles of projects in which construction enterprises involved as performers.

The Association of Change Management Professionals (USA) [1] offers a unified document designed

to improve change management processes at enterprises - "STANDARD FOR CHANGE MANAGEMENT". To date, this association unites the largest number of participants from different countries around the topic of change management.

The standard states that there are many types of change and there is no single universal change management tool. At the same time, the standard emphasizes strategic changes and the most important role of project management in the process of shaping the desired future of the organization. The standard was first published in 2014. The change management standard describes the area of knowledge, established norms, processes, tasks, skills and abilities necessary for change management practitioners. It is intended for individuals and organizations and provides an objective assessment of skills and abilities to enable more effective recruitment, training, consulting and investment related to change management. Can be applied to any type of organization, including public, private or community organizations, and to any type of change, regardless of complexity, scale, duration, geography or culture.

Changes are initiated at different levels of the organization, but the most important connection is between the processes of strategic planning and change management. Strategic management sets the vision and measures to achieve it, ensuring the achievement of expected benefits and return on investment. The vision shows why the changes are necessary and the risks that await the organization if the changes do not take place.

The stated vision creates a fundamental link between strategic planning and change management:

- provides clear direction and focus for the organization and stakeholders;
- promises that high results and the expected effect will be achieved;
- coordinates the efforts of managers and all interested parties to move according to the general plan;
- acts as a guide for decision-making, communication and interaction.

Successful change requires leaders to inspire, help understand the vision, and guide the organization toward the desired benefits.

The development of project management and its penetration into various spheres of human activity allows to systematize existing knowledge and use it effectively. Today, the rational use of resources and time is a priority task in many types of activities, and real estate construction is no exception. The world practice of using a project approach to managing tasks of any complexity has long proven its usefulness in practice [2-4].

A growing trend is noted by the number of domestic companies that have implemented a quality management system based on ISO at their enterprises (International Organization for Standardization - an international organization that develops standards for various fields of activity, accepted throughout the world, compliance with which guarantees the quality of service provision or production of products under the conditions of maximum effective use of resources and minimal impact on the environment) [5].

Certain shifts in the field of architectural and construction design have also been noted in recent times, where instead of traditional methods focused mainly only on functional expediency and aesthetics, designers have begun to apply innovative progressive approaches to the construction of new multifunctional buildings. A wide arsenal of technical and technological, engineering, artistic and stylistic innovations and modern possibilities of IT technologies have made qualitative changes in the thinking of architects and significantly expanded the possibilities of designing various buildings and structures [6].

Applying modern elements of project management, it is advisable to improve the process of making changes, which can be used as a methodological basis for operational activity.

Table 1

A five-stage model for improving the process of implementing changes

Stage		Action	Conducting an assessment
1	The action of factors under the influence of which the organization (or certain of its structural elements) must change	– study of the current state of the organization; – preparation of documentation that clearly outlines the key factors of business development; – development of goals for improvement of activity results; – determination of the desired results of behavior	– consumer satisfaction; – business development factors; – organizational culture; – an object in need of improvement; – previous experience of changes; – employees and managers, regarding their opinion regarding future changes
2	Establishing the direction and characteristics of changes	– formation of individual plans for managing improvement of work results; – unification of individual plans for management of improvement of work results; – development of 90-day action plans	– the current state of the enterprise's activity; – the scale of changes that are planned to be implemented to achieve the set goals
3	Determining what the organization needs for its changes	– formation of a team for implementation of changes; – involvement of the necessary specialists to carry out changes; – informing employees at each stage of changes	– available resources of the organization; – financial capabilities of the organization to purchase additional resources; – opportunities to attract investors; – the future (forecasted) state of the enterprise
4	Clarifying motivational tactics and strengthening creative personnel management	– application of methods by senior management and managers to reduce the level of tension in the team and strengthen the feeling of employees' faith in their competence, comfort, employees' confidence in the need for changes	– existing creative potential of the organization; – formal and informal leaders
5	Management of the organizational change process	– оголошення про проект працівникам та роз'яснення їм суті проекту; – розроблення плану виконання проекту та безпосереднє його виконання; – моніторинг процесу виконання проекту та проведення оцінки кінцевих результатів	– potential risks of the implemented changes; – obstacles that can prevent the implementation of the project

The financial firmness of companies shall be identified based on summarized individual operation aspects, which characterize clearly the available business model, its efficiency and resistance to external threats on the base of an integral approach to such an evaluation.

K – financial firmness of the company shall be determined according to the autonomy parameter, which characterizes the long-term company financial firmness and is commonly used for the financial firmness evaluation.

Initial drivers, which characterize comprehensively the company business model, the following are selected:

X_1 – efficiency of the available business model (efficiency parameter proposed in [3] (revenues to prime cost), which is used instead of conventional profitability parameters, since they are high volatile even during short evaluation periods, thus reducing modeling accuracy or even making impossible the use of data for further mathematic calculations;

X_2 – ratio of deterioration of company capital assets (cost of a deteriorated part of capital assets to their primary cost), share in units;

X_3 – return on assets ratio (revenues from sales of products, goods, works and services to average annual cost of capital assets);

X_4 – diversification of activities (number of granted operation licenses according to the Stock market infrastructure development agency of Ukraine (SMIDA));

X_5 – capital turnover ability factor (annual costs of sold products, goods, works and services according to current wholesale prices to average remaining capital balance for the same period);

X_6 – development firmness coefficient (calculated as a ratio of undistributed profits to the cost of assets).

The following stage is the determination of the driver influence on the company financial firmness (Table 2).

Table 2

Pair correlation coefficients for the “financial firmness”

	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5	X_6	K
X_1	1						
X_2	0,017637	1					
X_3	0,091373	0,044189	1				
X_4	0,220228	0,136484	0,179045	1			
X_5	-0,16486	-0,18642	-0,15112	-0,2356	1		
X_6	-0,0088	-0,08833	-0,40924	-0,1052	0,5532	1	
K	-0,22303	-0,09348	-0,66025	-0,2890	0,368521	0,462898	1

Source: calculated by authors based on public statement data of Ukrainian building companies

To determine the importance and the influence of X_1 - X_6 coefficients on the integral parameter of reorganization capacity of building companies, we will make a regression analysis (Table 2-5).

Table 3

Determination of a multiple correlation factor

Multiple R	0,738075
R-square	0,544755
Normalized R-square	0,464418
Standard error	0,66335
Observation	41

Parameters of factors of the get dependence (integral parameter of reorganization capacity of the company business model) are provided in Table 2. The

model is sufficiently accurate and explains the variability of resulting factor K depending on explaining factors 54,5%.

Table 4

Results of dispersion analysis

	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	6	17,90281	2,983802	6,780854	8,62E-05
Remain	34	14,96113	0,440033		
Total	40	32,86395			

According to data provided in Table 4, parameters of the linear equation have the following values: $a_0=0,349$; $a_1=-0,003$; $a_2=-0,0001$; $a_3=-0,057$; $a_4=-0,023$; $a_5=0,0534$; $a_6=0,0026$. The multiple correlation factor R is 0,738 – connection between the dependent

variable and influencing factors is rather close. The R_2 value says that the reorganization capacity of the business model is by 55% explained by variables included into the integral parameter obtained due to modeling.

Table 5

The coefficients' parameters of the obtained equation

	Coefficient	Standard error	t-statistics	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95,0%	Upper 95,0%
K	0,349	0,247282	1,412	0,166	-0,1533	0,8518	-0,1533	0,8518
X_1	-0,003	0,003468	-0,996	0,325	-0,0105	0,0035	-0,0105	0,0035
X_2	-0,0001	0,001597	-0,081	0,0935	-0,003	0,0031	-0,00338	0,0031
X_3	-0,057	0,013591	-4,229	0,0001	-0,085	-0,029	-0,08509	-0,029
X_4	-0,023	0,025202	-0,89308	0,378	-0,073	0,0287	-0,07372	0,0287
X_5	0,053	0,047923	0,91141	0,073	-0,044	0,1508	-0,044	0,1507
X_6	0,0026	0,003	0,873	0,388	-0,003	0,0087	-0,00349	0,0087

As a result, the model of the linear regression related to the reorganization capacity of building company's personnel is as follows:

$$K = 0,35 - 0,003 \cdot X_1 - 0,0001 \cdot X_2 - 0,057 \cdot X_3 - 0,023 \cdot X_4 + 0,053 \cdot X_5 + 0,0026 \cdot X_6 \quad (1)$$

where, X_1 – is the efficiency parameter (revenues to prime cost), X_2 – deterioration level of company capital assets (cost of a deteriorated part of capital assets to their primary cost), X_3 – return on assets ratio, X_4 – diversification of activities, X_5 – capital turnover

ability factor, X_6 – development firmness coefficient (ratio of undistributed profits to the cost of assets).

It is proposed to present the general management system of adaptation of the enterprise as a cyclical movement, which consists of the following stages:

- analysis and assessment of the conditions of the enterprise in the external (including the study of cyclical factors) and internal environment of its operation;

- identification of weaknesses and bottlenecks, strengths and capabilities of the enterprise, forecasting areas of enterprise development;
- formation of the mechanism of the enterprise's reaction to possible negative changes in the external and internal environment of functioning;
- development and implementation of mechanisms for managing the adaptation of the enterprise to changes at the level of organizational and economic, legal, technological and social components;
- monitoring, control and coordination of the main stages and elements of the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to change;
- adjustment of the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to changes with change of operating conditions.

The stages and essence of the components according to the theoretical blocks of formation of the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to changes are allocated:

- 1) theoretical foundations of the management system of adaptation to change: definition of the essence, type of transformation, main purpose, main tasks, subjects, objects, principles, mechanisms of the management system of adaptation to change in four components: organizational and economic, legal, technological, social;
- 2) methodological principles of enterprise management system for adaptation to changes: theoretical approaches to enterprise management, combination of system elements, development of approaches to adaptation management for each component of the management system for adaptation to change;
- 3) modeling of the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to changes: means and tools of construction, analysis and estimation of economic and mathematical models on components of the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to changes;
- 4) instrumental support of the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to changes: tools of analysis and assessment of preconditions; business models for four components; system formation and implementation software; instructions, regulations, etc.;
- 5) organizational and practical support of the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to changes: analysis and assessment of prerequisites; component planning; organization of implementation of measures; motivation of staff to implement the management system of adaptation of the enterprise to change; control and coordination of system components; analysis and evaluation of system efficiency; adjustment of elements.

The instrumental base for modeling strategic performance as a management model for the company's adaptation to changes, which has a number of advantages in practical use by companies: it is based on the vision, mission and main development tasks formed by the company; takes into account factors of cyclical-ity, which are a reflection of existing trends in the economy of the world and the country and directly affect the development of the enterprise; provides opportunities to carry out a comprehensive assessment of the external and internal environment of the enterprise, to calculate and forecast the psychological and qualification level of personnel and the level of perception of changes by

these employees; relies on the theoretical foundations of the process approach when developing mechanisms for managing individual components based on business process management; is developed in accordance with the main functions of management, which makes it possible to take into account the sequence of actions and the formation of regulations for the management of enterprises.

In turn, the main components of the management system for the adaptation of enterprises to changes take into account the need to systematize and manage auxiliary processes: infrastructure and information; the need for feedback, adjustment of the developed measures of the strategic performance management regulation as a result of monitoring and control over the consequences of its implementation.

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